

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCES AS PROPHYLAXIS AGAINST “JA’PA” SYNDROME: EFFECT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL KNOWLEDGE ON NIGERIA OPTION IN EMERGING WORKFORCE FROM LAGOS STATE UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF MEDICINE (LASUCOM)

T. A. John,^{1,2} W. A. Akingbade,³ R. O. Okuneye,^{4,5} O. I. Olateju^{3,6}

¹Department of Pharmacology, Therapeutics, and Toxicology, Faculty of Basic Clinical Sciences, Lagos State University College of Medicine, Lagos, Nigeria; ²Entrepreneurial Training Unit, Lagos State University College of Medicine, Lagos, Nigeria; ³Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences, Lagos State University, Lagos, Nigeria; ⁴Department of Human Kinetics, Sports, and Health Education, Faculty of Education, Lagos State University, Lagos, Nigeria; ⁵Directorate of Quality Assurance, Lagos State University, Lagos, Nigeria; ⁶Post Graduate School, Lagos State University, Lagos, Nigeria.

Corresponding Author

Prof. T. A. John, Department of Pharmacology, Therapeutics, and Toxicology, Faculty of Basic Clinical Sciences, Lagos State University College of Medicine, Lagos, Nigeria.

Email: theresa.john@lasucom.edu.ng

Abstract

Background: Health professions entrepreneurship in Nigeria is still too low to cover the vast opportunities of diversified roles in the Nigerian Health Sector that could be areas of job satisfaction and wealth generation for migrating (“*ja’pa*”) young health professionals (YHPs). Each person can have multiple intelligences and can be strong or weak in particular intelligences. With respect to migration and entrepreneurial intentions, we may improve certain intelligences in emerging workforce through educational intervention.

Purpose: We wanted to know the effect of Intelligence on Entrepreneurship in graduating YHPs of Lagos State University College of Medicine (LASUCOM) using indicators of multiple intelligences. The aims were to evaluate the effect of Transformative Knowledge on Entrepreneurial Confidence; the effect of Entrepreneurial Knowledge on Entrepreneurial Confidence; the extent to which Transformative Knowledge affects Nigeria Option; and the extent to which Entrepreneurial Knowledge affects Nigeria Option.

Methodology: A structured 5-point Likert scale questionnaire was used to survey the group of graduating doctors that completed a 3-day transformative course on entrepreneurship.

Results: Correlation of indicators of Intelligence and Entrepreneurship were positive, moderate to strong, and Pearson’s $r(21)$ ranged from 0.54 to 0.68. Transformative Knowledge significantly contributes towards the variability in Entrepreneurial Confidence and Nigeria Option (36.27% and 29.18 % respectively, $p < 0.05$ in both cases). Entrepreneurial Knowledge significantly ($p < 0.05$) contributes 46.21% and 42.68% to variability in Entrepreneurial Confidence and Nigeria Option respectively. The results of survey of graduating YHPs of LASUCOM reveals a link between education and “*ja’pa*” syndrome. Transformative Knowledge and Entrepreneurial Knowledge gained through a specialized motivational training on entrepreneurship correlate positively and significantly with both Entrepreneurial Confidence and Nigeria Option.

Conclusion: Transformative entrepreneurial training is related to the option of emerging workforce to stay in Nigeria. By unfolding local opportunities through transformative entrepreneurial education, Nigeria may be able to curb excessive brain drain of young health professionals. Personal vision and mission should be greater than whatever push or pull factors await the young health professional on graduation.

Keywords: *Ja'pa* syndrome, Young health professional, Entrepreneurship, Multiple intelligences, Transformative knowledge.

Introduction

The Nigerian Health Sector has suffered from factors that have been substantiated by various researchers, over the past two decades.^{1,2,3,4} Brain drain (“*ja’pa*” syndrome) of young health professionals (YHPs) and health professionals that are more advanced in their careers has been chronically a source of socio-economic loss to Nigeria and other African countries.^{5,1,6,7,8} Health professions entrepreneurship in Nigeria is still too low to cover the vast opportunities of diversified roles in the Nigerian Health Sector that could be areas of job satisfaction and wealth generation for migrating young health professionals (YHPs). This may be because innovation has been peculiarly challenging in Africa.⁹ Nigeria has spent \$11 billion on medical services abroad in ten years.¹⁰ Brain drain of scientists in Nigeria is a recognized hindrance to progress and development.^{11,12} Research papers and reviews addressing issues of migration and medical tourism have focussed on factors external to the migrants – push factors and pull factors.^{13,14} Factors internal to the would-be migrants have not received enough attention. It is not known whether missing competencies in YHPs have significant effects on their choice to migrate or to be involved in health sector entrepreneurialships at home. There must be a gap in the education system that has been turning out YHPs, resulting in persistence of brain drain and flight of human capital from the workforce of the struggling Nigerian Health Sector. Gardner.^{15,16} suggested that every person can have multiple intelligences and can be strong or weak in particular intelligences. With respect to migration and entrepreneurial intentions, we may improve certain intelligences in the emerging workforce through educational intervention. To educate the emerging workforce for “greener pasture at home” has become an imperative for the Nigerian academia against the backdrop of Health Sector problems.¹⁷

Intelligence may be described as “biopsychological potential to process information that can be activated in a cultural setting to solve problems or create products that are of value in a culture.”¹⁶

Entrepreneurial knowledge consists of the identified thematic areas that constitute the basis of entrepreneurship, e.g. making a business plan, business administration, market analysis, communication, and discipline-specific knowledge. Transformative knowledge is knowledge that shifts perspective and it has three dimensions: psychological (changes in understanding of the self), convictional (revision of belief systems), and behavioral (changes in lifestyle).¹⁸ Brain drain is “departure of educated or professional people from one country, economic sector, or field for another usually for better pay or living conditions.”¹⁹ Brain drain from Nigeria, nicknamed *ja apa* or *ja’pa* (Yoruba: to break away from difficulty) syndrome is the chronic exodus of middle-class and highly skilled Nigerians. Brain drain is viewed by some as negative^{20,21} and by others as positive.²² However, brain drain may represent inability or refusal of the migrants to face the Nigerian terrain. The option to stay in Nigeria if one could migrate represents certain confidence that may be a result of some competencies. Entrepreneurial confidence in this study is regarded as the mental state of being ready to face the challenge of entrepreneurship and to succeed with the necessary supports.

Certainly, one must have multiple intelligences to succeed in a difficult terrain, which the Nigerian Health Sector has been, rather than flee from it. Gardner¹⁵ in his book: *Frames of Mind: The Theory of Multiple Intelligences*, indicates that people have different kinds of “intelligences.” Robert Sternberg developed the triarchic theory of intelligence seeing intelligence as comprising of three parts: practical, creative, and analytical intelligence.²³ We are left to ask if the graduating YHPs from Nigerian medical schools are actually sufficiently prepared for the Nigerian terrain. Are there missing competencies in the Nigerian Health Sector workforce, resulting in brain drain? Educational intervention is necessary in changing competencies. In particular, entrepreneurial education is necessary to encourage the emerging workforce to stay in Nigeria and contribute independently to their chosen fields. This work seeks to know if indicators of multiple

intelligences (Entrepreneurial Knowledge and Transformative Knowledge gained through a special workshop) play a role in readiness to do entrepreneurship (Entrepreneurial Confidence) and decision to stay in Nigeria (Nigeria Option) in graduating YHPs of LASUCOM. The specific research objectives in this study are:

1. to evaluate the effect of Transformative Knowledge on Entrepreneurial Confidence
2. to evaluate the effect of Entrepreneurial Knowledge on Entrepreneurial Confidence
3. to determine the extent to which Transformative Knowledge affects Nigeria Option
4. to determine the extent to which Entrepreneurial Knowledge affects Nigeria Option

In order to achieve these objectives, the following hypotheses were formulated for testing:

- H₀1: Transformative Knowledge does not affect Entrepreneurial Confidence in graduating YHPs of LASUCOM
- H₀2: Entrepreneurial Knowledge does not affect Entrepreneurial Confidence in graduating YHPs of LASUCOM
- H₀3: Transformative Knowledge does not play a role in Nigeria Option in graduating YHPs of LASUCOM
- H₀4: Entrepreneurial Knowledge does not play a role in Nigeria Option in graduating YHPs of LASUCOM.

Methods

Data Collection

A descriptive survey using a structured 5-point Likert scale questionnaire was done to obtain information from a targeted finite population of interest, the group of YHPs that completed a transformative course on entrepreneurship. The course was given by two multidisciplinary medical entrepreneurs with advanced medical qualifications and business administration degrees and one cognitive psychologist, who all run multiple businesses and training consultancies. The students were from Lagos State University College of Medicine, a leader in entrepreneurial education amongst Nigerian medical schools. After participating in the 2-day online plus one-day physical transformative course on medical entrepreneurship, they were judged as having knowledge of entrepreneurship. Twenty-three

students attending last day of training were available for this survey. In the structured questionnaire, the dependent and independent variables were represented by two indicators each. Each indicator was represented by five positive statements. The first section of the questionnaire sought their Knowledge Appreciation (KA) using five positive statements. The independent variable, Intelligence, was indicated by Transformative Knowledge (TK) and Entrepreneurial Knowledge (EK) both of which were represented by five positive statements each on the questionnaire. The dependent variable, Entrepreneurship, was indicated by Entrepreneurial Confidence (EC) and Nigeria Option (NO) both of which were represented by five positive statements each on the questionnaire. The independent variable, Intelligence, was investigated for its role on the dependent variable, Entrepreneurship, in the students who were adjudged to have Knowledge Appreciation. Participants were given to answer one option out of five for each statement: strongly disagree, disagree, undecided, agree, or strongly agree. Questionnaires were answered and returned at the venue. The YHPs surveyed are potential Health Sector entrepreneurs and potential migrants to developed countries. Bivariate data was studied with Microsoft Excel® program to obtain descriptive statistics, regression analysis, and coefficients of multiple determination.

Validation of Research Instrument

Content validity of the questionnaire were determined by central tendencies of descriptive statistics obtained. Five statements measuring an indicator are expected to return similar values of mean, mode, and median for content validity.

Data Analysis

The questionnaire was validated as having reliable statement combinations as structured. Data from questionnaires was coded and extracted unto Excel® spreadsheets. Values given to answers were: strongly disagree = 1, disagree = 2, undecided = 3, agree = 4, strongly agree = 5. Descriptive statistics: modes, medians, means ± SE were computed. Paired students t-tests were done to show significance of differences at $p < 0.05$ for groups of interest. Bivariate data were used to plot scatter charts to visualize any correlation between dependent and independent variables. Correlation analyses (Pearson, r) were done to

determine direction and strengths of relationships between independent and dependent variables. Pearson correlation was used because of the low value of N (23). The function CORREL in Excel® spread sheet was used to generate coefficient of correlation in the bivariate data sets. This indicates how closely the data fit on a line. The strengths of correlation were interpreted following Dancey and Reidy²⁴ as 1=perfect, 7-9 = strong, 4-6 = moderate, and 1-3 = weak. The slope of the linear correlation line was also obtained from the automatically generated equation in Excel®. Regression analyses were done by automatic generation of R^2 , coefficient of multiple determination, on the linear plots of bivariate data sets indicating % cause of variation of one variable on another variable or variation of dependent variable that is directly related to variation of independent variable. P values of the significance of the correlations were generated using the function TDIST in Excel® with the test or T-statistics for n-2 degrees of freedom for one tailed test. The value alpha was set at 0.05; any results with $p > 0.05$ was rejected as random or purely due to chance or not giving enough confidence and the null hypothesis would be accepted. Data was analysed to determine relationship of independent variable and dependent variable.

Results

Young Health Professionals' Appreciation of Transformative Training in Entrepreneurship

The YHPs who participated in the survey had Knowledge Appreciation ranging 4.52 ± 0.15 – 4.78 ± 0.09 (minimum value = 0; maximal value = 5) after their transformative entrepreneurship course and thus were considered to have some background in entrepreneurship (Table 1). The impact of transformative training was shown by the level of Transformational Knowledge (TK) in the young health professionals and this ranged from 4.22 ± 0.17 to 4.52 ± 0.11 (minimum value = 0; maximal value = 5) (Table 2).

Entrepreneurial Knowledge in Young Health Professionals who received transformative training in entrepreneurship.

In the YHPs who participated in the survey, the indicators for Entrepreneurial Knowledge, EK 1 to EK 5, gave values ranging from 4.17 ± 0.15 –

4.52 ± 0.11 (minimum value = 0; maximal value = 5) (Table 3).

Entrepreneurial Confidence in Young Health Professionals who received transformative training in entrepreneurship

In the YHPs who participated in the survey, the indicators for Entrepreneurial Confidence, EC 1 to EC 5, gave values ranging from 2.91 ± 0.26 – 4.36 ± 0.12 (minimum value = 0; maximal value = 5) (Table 4).

Nigeria Option in Young Health Professionals who received transformative training in entrepreneurship.

In the YHPs who participated in the survey, the indicators for Nigeria Option, NO 1 to NO 5, gave values ranging from 3.48 ± 0.20 – 4.18 ± 0.15 (minimum value = 0; maximal value = 5) (Table 5).

Results of bivariate analyses of relationships between intelligence and entrepreneurship

Using Microsoft Excel®, data obtained from the questionnaire survey was transformed into graphs (Figures 1 and 2). Scatter plots revealed pattern of relationships between bivariate sets. Calculated Pearson's correlation coefficients (r values) differed from slopes.

Rejection of null hypothesis

Disprove of H_01 : Transformative Knowledge does not affect Entrepreneurial Confidence in graduating young doctors of LASUCOM

Pearson's correlation coefficient, $r(21)$, was 0.602, $p = 0.013$ for one-tail and 0.002 for two tail t-tests. Coefficient of multiple determination shows that 36.27% variability in Entrepreneurial Confidence (Figure 1A) can be attributed to variability in Transformative Knowledge. There is a less than 5% chance that this result can be obtained randomly, thus Hypothesis 1 is rejected. Transformative Knowledge correlates positively and moderately with Entrepreneurial Confidence in the graduating young doctors of LASUCOM surveyed, $p < 0.05$.

Disprove of H_02 : Entrepreneurial Knowledge does not affect Entrepreneurial Confidence in graduating young doctors of LASUCOM.

Pearson's correlation coefficient, $r(21)$, was 0.6798, $p = 0.007$ for one-tail and 0.0004 for two tail t-tests. Coefficient of multiple determination shows that 46.21% variability in Entrepreneurial Confidence (Figure 1B) can be attributed to variability in Entrepreneurial Knowledge. There is

a less than 5% chance that this result can be obtained randomly, thus Hypothesis 2 is rejected. Entrepreneurial Knowledge correlates positively and strongly with Entrepreneurial Confidence in the graduating young doctors of LASUCOM surveyed, $p < 0.05$.

Disprove of H_03 : Transformative Knowledge does not play a role in Nigeria Option in graduating young doctors of LASUCOM

A

B

Figure 1: Entrepreneurial Confidence depends moderately on indicators of intelligence, Transformative Knowledge and Entrepreneurial Knowledge, in graduating young doctors of LASUCOM.

Table 1: Knowledge Appreciation of graduating YHPs of Lagos State University College of Medicine (LASUCOM) who participated in a 2-day online plus 1-day physical course on medical entrepreneurship.

INDICATOR		QUESTIONNAIRE STATEMENTS	DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS				
			MODE	MEDIAN	MEAN	STDEV	SE
KNOWLEDGE APPRECIATION	KA 1	the course is useful	5	5.00	4.78	0.42	0.09
	KA 2	the course is necessary	5	5.00	4.70	0.47	0.10
	KA 3	the course is timely	5	5.00	4.52	0.73	0.15
	KA 4	the course is important	5	5.00	4.70	0.47	0.10
	KA 5	the course helped me	5	5.00	4.57	0.51	0.11

Table 2: Transformational Knowledge gained by graduating YHPs of Lagos State University College of Medicine (LASUCOM) who participated in a 2-day online plus 1-day physical course on medical entrepreneurship

INDICATOR		QUESTIONNAIRE STATEMENTS	DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS				
			MODE	MEDIAN	MEAN	STDEV	SE
TRANSFORMATIONAL KNOWLEDGE	TK 1	the course changed my perspective	5	5.00	4.52	0.51	0.11
	TK 2	the course got me making resolutions	5	4.00	4.39	0.66	0.14
	TK 3	the course increased my interest in entrepreneurship	5	5.00	4.43	0.90	0.19
	TK 4	the course got me thinking	4	4.00	4.35	0.71	0.15
	TK 5	the course got me planning	5	4.00	4.22	0.80	0.17

Table 3. Entrepreneurial Knowledge in graduating YHPs of Lagos State University College of Medicine (LASUCOM) who participated in a 2-day online plus 1-day physical course on medical entrepreneurship.

INDICATOR		QUESTIONNAIRE STATEMENTS	DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS				
			MODE	MEDIAN	MEAN	STDEV	SE
EMPRENEURIAL KNOWLEDGE	EK 1	I now know more about business opportunities in Nigeria	4	4.00	4.22	0.74	0.15
	EK 2	I now know more things I can do in Nigeria	4	4.00	4.22	0.60	0.13
	EK 3	I now know more about entrepreneurship	5	5.00	4.52	0.51	0.11
	EK 4	I now know more about how I can start a business	4	4.00	4.17	0.65	0.14
	EK 5	I now know more about what businesses I would like to go into	4	4.00	4.17	0.72	0.15

Table 4: Entrepreneurial Confidence in graduating YHPs of Lagos State University College of Medicine (LASUCOM) who participated in a 2-day online plus 1-day physical course on medical entrepreneurship.

INDICATOR		QUESTIONNAIRE STATEMENTS	DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS				
			MODE	MEDIAN	MEAN	STDEV	SE
ENTREPRENEURIAL CONFIDENCE	EC 1	I now know more about how to get help as an entrepreneur	4	4.00	4.14	0.64	0.13
	EC 2	I have decided to have an entrepreneur mentor	3	3.50	3.73	0.83	0.17
	EC 3	I now know more about how to succeed as an entrepreneur anywhere	4	4.00	4.36	0.58	0.12
	EC 4	I now know more about how to succeed as an entrepreneur in Nigeria	4	4.00	4.30	0.63	0.13
	EC 5	I now know of special funds available for entrepreneurial startups in Nigeria	2	3.00	2.91	1.27	0.26

Table 5. Nigeria Option in graduating YHPs of Lagos State University College of Medicine (LASUCOM) who participated in a 2-day online plus 1-day physical course on medical entrepreneurship.

INDICATOR		QUESTIONNAIRE STATEMENTS	DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS				
			MODE	MEDIAN	MEAN	STDEV	SE
NIGERIA OPTION	NO 1	I think of succeeding in Nigeria long term	5	4.00	3.91	1.00	0.21
	NO 2	I am optimistic Nigeria is my best option for success	3	3.00	3.57	0.84	0.18
	NO 3	I think I want to return to Nigeria if I migrate	4	4.00	3.64	1.22	0.25
	NO 4	I am confident I will succeed as an entrepreneur in Nigeria	4	4.00	4.18	0.73	0.15
	NO 5	The course increased my interest in staying in Nigeria	3	3.00	3.48	0.95	0.20

A

B

Figure 2: Nigeria Option depends strongly on indicators of intelligence, Transformative Knowledge and Entrepreneurial Knowledge, in graduating young doctors of LASUCOM.

Figure 3: Alternatives faced by young health professionals in a struggling health sector.

Pearson's correlation coefficient, $r(21)$, was 0.540, $p = 0.021$ for one-tail and 0.0078 for two tail t -tests. The slope of the scatter plot was 0.961 showing near perfect correlation. Coefficient of multiple determination shows that 29.18% variability in Nigeria Option (Figure 2A) can be attributed to variability in Transformative Knowledge. There is a less than 5% chance that this result can be obtained randomly, thus Hypothesis 3 is rejected. Transformative Knowledge correlates positively and moderately with Nigeria Option in the graduating young doctors of LASUCOM surveyed, $p < 0.05$.

Disprove of H_04 : Entrepreneurial Knowledge does not play a role in Nigeria Option in graduating young doctors of LASUCOM

Pearson's correlation coefficient, $r(21)$, was 0.653, $p = 0.0084$ for one-tail and 0.0007 for two tail t -tests. The slope of the scatter plot was 1 showing a perfect correlation. Coefficient of multiple determination shows that 42.68% variability in Nigeria Option (Figure 2B) can be attributed to variability in Entrepreneurial Knowledge. There is a less than 5% chance that this result can be obtained randomly, thus Hypothesis 4 is rejected. Entrepreneurial Knowledge correlates positively and strongly with Nigeria Option in the graduating young doctors of LASUCOM surveyed, $p < 0.05$.

Discussion

The present study was conducted using a group of students that participated in a short transformative course on entrepreneurship. The course was

designed to be transformative, activating multiple intelligences in the participants. As mentioned in the Introduction, Transformative Knowledge is knowledge that shifts perspective and it has three dimensions: psychological (changes in understanding of the self), convictional (revision of belief systems), and behavioral (changes in lifestyle).¹⁸ According, the training modules we used were to actualize in participants the following intelligences: entrepreneurial intelligence for personal contributions, emotional intelligence to respond to local needs, scientific intelligence to be innovative, cultural intelligence for adaptability, and recognition of green pastures at home for job satisfaction. The results show that, apart from push and pull factors that are usually studied,^{25,1,26} it is important to study inherent student factors that may help us understand "ja'pa" syndrome and its long-term remedies. This survey reveals a link between education and "ja'pa" syndrome. From our investigation, the indicator of the independent variable (Intelligence), Transformative Knowledge, correlates positively and moderately with both Entrepreneurial Confidence and Nigeria Option in the graduating YHPs of LASUCOM surveyed, $p < 0.05$ in both cases. Similarly, another indicator of Intelligence, Entrepreneurial Knowledge correlates positively and strongly with both Entrepreneurial Confidence and Nigeria Option in the graduating young doctors of LASUCOM surveyed, $p < 0.05$ in both cases. A gap in education may be sustaining the decades old "ja'pa" syndrome in Nigeria. The present study is

strong evidence indicating interesting relationships between indicators of intelligence and indicators of entrepreneurship as well as indicators of the option to work in Nigeria. We can confidently say that it is important to provide transformative training that generates change agents as well as entrepreneurial education that generates entrepreneurial confidence to graduating young health professionals in Nigerian medical schools. The prognosis of “*ja’pa*” syndrome in Nigeria partly depends on this educational intervention. Transformative Knowledge and Entrepreneurial Knowledge may be good prophylactics for the decades old “*ja’pa*” syndrome in Nigeria.

Nigeria’s young health professionals need to be educated for and supported for greener pastures at home as a preferred alternative to migration (Figure 3). The random utility theory says that “every individual is a rational decision-maker, maximizing utility relative to his or her choices.”²⁷ People choose what they prefer; according to where they yield maximum utility. The medium utility in *Health Sector entrepreneurs in Nigeria* should exceed the maximum utility in *migration to developed countries*, if Nigeria wants to retain her young health professionals and emerging workforce. Perspective is subjective. A study on perspectives has this limitation but a study of perspectives is important because perspective can be the psychological basis of decision. Perspectives can be radical, incremental, or evolving and education can make a difference. Perspective change is important in training and mentoring for Africans that suffer effects of flight of human capital or brain drain, especially within the emerging workforce. The random utility theory is pertinent in this respect. We need to understand what perspectives are the basis of the decisions of young health professionals and the emerging workforce of Nigeria.

The significance of this study is that it shows we can improve cost-effect benefits of medical school educational efforts for the Nigerian Health Sector and the economy. The initial insight we have here from this small population (N=23) indicates that relationships between migration, entrepreneurship, and development²⁸ in the context of Africans need a deeper consideration. The findings warrant further investigation with a

more rigorous design; the picture may become clearer long-term. This goes beyond what governments can do to impact brain drain, as suggested.^{29,30,31}

We cannot predict the long-term effects of the transformative course in this report. Ryan and coworkers³² in examining sixteen reviews on transformative learning in health professions published between 2012 and 2022 concluded that applying transformative learning theory in curriculum design, program evaluation and healthcare professional education can be beneficial. A scoping review³³ revealed that transformative learning as a pedagogic tool in graduate medical education was closely linked with professionalism training and professional identity formation. Vipler and coworkers³⁴ in observing the transformative learning of medical trainees during the COVID-19 pandemic opined that if leaders in academic medicine desire to create enlightened change agents through transformative learning, such education must continue throughout graduate medical education and beyond. Transformative learning experiences, e.g. rural and longitudinal placements, are deemed important in preparing a future workforce to address local needs.³⁵ In this report, against the threat of brain drain (*ja’pa* syndrome), transformative learning as a direct educational intervention is indicated for emerging workforce in the Nigerian Health Sector.

The WHO has indicated that medical schools have social accountability.^{36,37} Developing teachers and developing learners are both important.^{38,39} Based on the finding of this study, we recommend that Nigerian medical schools develop special transformative education modules that help to activate multiple intelligences that are crucial for the career successes of YHP in their own home country. Such models can be brief, need not disturb established curricula, and may be delivered compulsorily at the point of graduation. They should help young health professionals in decision making and in becoming change agents both for entrepreneurship at home and for migration for national advantage. They should empower YHPs to thrive in the Nigerian socio-economic terrain, and not flee (*ja’pa*) from it for greener pastures abroad.⁴⁰ By unfolding local opportunities through transformative

entrepreneurial education, Nigeria may be able to curb excessive brain drain of young health professionals. Personal vision and mission should be greater than whatever push or pull factors await the young health professional on graduation. The medical schools systems may help turn the tide from young migrants to young nation builders.

Conclusion

This study sheds light on the role of transformative knowledge and entrepreneurial knowledge on career intentions of young doctors that may help to resolve “*japa*” syndrome. This study establishes that transformative education can support Entrepreneurial Confidence and Nigeria Option with strengths of 36.27% and 29.18% respectively and that entrepreneurial education can support Entrepreneurial Confidence and Nigeria Option with strengths of 46.21% and 42.68 % respectively.

Acknowledgments

Deep appreciation go to the following trainers for providing excellent training in the transformative workshop and for their collaboration with the Entrepreneurial Training Unit of Lagos State University College of Medicine:

Joel Akande, MBBS, LLB, MBA, Founder and MD/CEO, Strategic Insights Healthcare, Lagos.

Abdul Kokori, PhD, Certified Thinking Instructor and Managing Consultant of Brain Connections Associates, Abuja.

Mario Adelaja, MBChB, GHPM, GHLIHM, FRSPH, MBA, Project Management Consultant, Health Systems Reform Advocate, Director, Case Management and Care Coordination, Reliance Health.

The Entrepreneurial Training Unit at LASUCOM is supported by the College’s Executive Committee (ExCo) to which the authors are grateful.

Declarations

Funding

The training course was supported by participants’ fees and a large subsidy from the College ExCo

Conflicts of Interest/Competing Interests

None

Code availability

None

Authors’ Contributions

TAJ: idea, research design, survey, data analysis, documentation and reporting; WAA: Supervisor/Consultant (Business Administration); ROO: Supervisor/Consultant (Tertiary Education); OIO: research and statistics methodologies.

Ethics approval

Data studied is from the feedback mechanism of the Directorate for Skills Development and Entrepreneurship, LASU (LASU-DSDE) and is used with permission. No sensitive or risky information is utilized.

Consent to participate

All participants freely consented to participate in the survey.

Consent for publication

The Entrepreneurial Training Unit at LASUCOM and LASU-DSDE consented to the publication of these findings as part of their functional roles.

References

1. Lawal L, Lawal AO, Amosu OP, Muhammad-Olodo AO, Abdurashed N, Abdullah KU, Kuza PB, Aborode AT, Adebisi YA, Kareem AA, Aliu A, Elelu TM, Murwira T. The COVID-19 pandemic and health workforce brain drain in Nigeria. *Int J Equity Health* 2022;21(1):174, doi: 10.1186/s12939-022-01789-z. PMID: 36471333; PMCID: PMC9724397.
2. Oleribe OO, Ezieme IP, Oladipo O, Akinola EP, Udofia D, and Taylor-Robinson SD. Industrial action by healthcare workers in Nigeria in 2013 – 2015: an inquiry into causes, consequences and control — a cross-sectional descriptive study. *Human Resources for Health* 2016;14(1):46, doi: 10.1186/s12960-016-0142-7.
3. Adetayo JO. A study of factors influencing brain drain among medical personnel in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Health and Biomedical Sciences* 2010;9(1), doi: 10.4314/njhbs.v9i1.60969.
4. Hagopian A, Ofosu A, Fatusi A, Biritwum R, Essel A, Garry Hart L *et al.*. The flight of physicians from West Africa: views of African physicians and implications for policy. *Soc Sci Med* 2005;61(8):1750-60, doi: 10.1016/j.socscimed.2005.03.027.
5. Adejoro L. 57,000 nurses left Nigeria in five years – NANNM. *Punch* 2022;

<https://punchng.com/57000-nurses-left-nigeria-in-five-years-nannm/#:~:text=The%20President%20of%20the%20National,spanning%20from%202017%20to%202022>

6. Adeloye D, David RA, Olaogun AA, Auta A, Adesokan A, Gadanya M, Opele JK, Owagbemi O, Iseolorunkanmi A. Health workforce and governance: the crisis in Nigeria. *Hum Resour Health*. 2017;15(1):32, doi: 10.1186/s12960-017-0205-4. PMID: 28494782; PMCID: PMC5427605.

7. Ike SO. The health workforce crisis: the brain drain scourge. *Niger J Med* 2007; 16(3):204–211, doi:10.4314/NJM.V16I3.37308.

8. Nwagu-Emeka OC. Migration of international medical graduates: implications for the brain-drain. *Open Medical Journal* 2015;2:17-24, doi: 10.2174/1874220301401010017.

9. Nwaka S, Ochem A, Besson D, Ramirez B, Fakorede F, Botros S, Inyang U, Mgone C, Adae-Mensah I, Konde V, Nyasse B, Okole B, Guantai A, Loots G, Atadja P, Ndumbe P, Sanou I, Olesen O, Ridley R and Ilunga T. Analysis of pan-African Centres of excellence in health innovation highlights opportunities and challenges for local innovation and financing in the continent. *BMC International Health and Human Rights* 2012;12:11 <http://www.biomedcentral.com/1472-698X/12/11>

10. Oyekanmi S. Nigerians spend \$11 billion on medical services abroad in 10 years. *Nairametrics* 2021; <https://nairametrics.com/2021/08/31/nigerians-spend-11-billion-on-medical-services-abroad-in-10-years/>

11. Ojiugo GE, Chigozie RU, Eze IJ. Brain drain and sustainable development in Nigeria, 2000-2015. *University of Nigeria Journal of Political Economy* 2021; 11(1): 278-292.

12. Atta-Mensah J. Lessons from the field: The role of science, technology, and innovation in Africa's growth. *Blog Africa up close* blog of the Africa program The Wilson Center 2015; <https://africaupclose.wilsoncenter.org/the-role-of-science-technology-and-innovation-in-africas-growth-1/>

13. Awire E, Okumagba M. Medical education in Nigeria and migration: a mixed-methods study of how the perception of quality influences migration decision making. *MedEdPublish* 2020;9(1), DOI:10.15694/mep.2020.000001.1

14. Akinyemi O, Atilola O. Nigerian resident doctors on strike: insights from and policy implications of job satisfaction among resident doctors in a Nigerian teaching hospital. *Int J Health Plann Manage* 2013;28(1):e46-61, doi: 10.1002/hpm.2141. Epub 2012 Sep 7. PMID: 22961749.

15. Gardner HE. *Frames of Mind: The Theory of Multiple Intelligences*. Basic Books, Perseus Books Group, New York; 1983.

16. Gardner HE. *Intelligence reframed: Multiple intelligences for the 21st century*. Hachette UK; 2000, p.28.

17. John TA, Ofi AO. Health professions entrepreneurial education and the future workforce: a focus on the nursing profession in Nigeria. *Nig. Qt J. Hosp. Med.* 2021;31(1&2).

18. Clark MC, Wilson AL. Context and rationality in Mezirow's Theory of Transformational Learning. *Adult Education Quarterly* 1991;41, 75-91.

19. Merriam-Webster Dictionary. "Brain drain." Merriam-Webster.com Dictionary, Merriam-Webster, <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/brain%20drain>. Accessed 20 July 2023.

20. Wickramasekara P. Globalisation, international labour migration and the rights of migrant workers. *Third World Quarterly* 2008; vol. 29, issue 7, 1247-1264. DOI: 10.1080/01436590802386278

21. Omogbolagun T. JAPA: Over 137 students sponsored abroad absconded *Punch Newspapers* 2023; <https://punchng.com/japa-over-137-students-sponsored...> Accessed July 20 2023.

22. Abiru F. Is Nigeria's Brain Drain Actually a Net Gain? *Stears – Economy* 2019; <https://www.stears.co/article/is-nigerias-brain-drain-actually-a-net-gain/?amp-content=amp>

23. Sternberg, RJ. *Beyond IQ: A Triarchic Theory of Human Intelligence*. Cambridge University Press; 1985.

24. Dancy CP, Reidy J. *Statistics without maths for psychology* (4th ed.). Pearson/Prentice Hall; 2007.

25. Young J. *Brain Drain: Definition, Causes, Effects, and Examples*. Investopedia 2023;

https://www.investopedia.com/terms/b/brain_drain.asp, Accessed July 20 2023.

26. Odigwe C. Lagos state doctors are sacked for striking over pay. *BMJ* 2012; 344:e3512. doi: 10.1136/bmj.e3512.

27. Horowitz, JL. Advances in random utility models report of the workshop on advances in random utility models duke invitational symposium on choice modeling behavior. *Marketing Letters* 1994; 5(4): 311-322.

28. Naudé W, Siegel M, Marchand, K. Migration, entrepreneurship and development: critical questions. *IZA J Migration* 2017; 6: 5. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40176-016-0077-8>.

29. Adenipekun, A. The brain drain of healthcare professionals in Nigeria: The buck stops with government. *Voices*, Blavatnik School of Government, University of Oxford: January 4, 2023: <https://www.bsg.ox.ac.uk/blog/brain-drain-healthcare-professionals-nigeria-buck-stops-government>.

30. Ileyemi, M. Brain Drain: Nigeria now left with 55,000 doctors as 16,000 doctors emigrate in five years – Minister. *Health*, Premium Times, March 11, 2024: <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/health/health-news/676536-brain-drain-nigeria-now-left-with-55000-doctors-as-1600-emigrate-in-five-years-minister.html?tztc=1>.

31. Abisola, A. Brain drain and funding challenges in Nigeria's health sector. *Viewpoint*, Vanguard, January 16, 2024: <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2024/01/brain-drain-and-funding-challenges-in-nigerias-health-sector/>.

32. Ryan CL, Cant R, McAllister MM, Vanderburg R, Batty C. Transformative learning theory applications in health professional and nursing education: An umbrella review. *Nurse Educ Today*. 2022 Dec;119:105604. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2022.105604. Epub 2022 Oct 13. PMID: 36265209.

33. Vipler B, Knehans A, Rausa D, Haidet P, McCall-Hosenfeld J. Transformative Learning in Graduate Medical Education: A Scoping Review. *J Grad Med Educ*. 2021 Dec;13(6):801-814. doi: 10.4300/JGME-D-21-00065.1. Epub 2021 Dec 14. PMID: 35070093; PMCID: PMC8672835.

34. Vipler B, Snyder B, McCall-Hosenfeld J, Haidet P, Peyrot M, Stuckey H. Transformative learning of medical trainees during the COVID-19

pandemic: A mixed methods study. *PLoS One*. 2022 Sep 16;17(9):e0274683. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0274683. PMID: 36112640; PMCID: PMC9481004.

35. Müller J, Reardon C, Coetzee F, Bester J, Dube K, Hanekom S, du Plessis E, Couper I. Transformative learning through participation: experiences at a rural clinical training site in South Africa. *BMC Med Educ*. 2022 Mar 16;22(1):183. doi: 10.1186/s12909-022-03233-w. PMID: 35296325; PMCID: PMC8928645.

36. World Health Organization. Defining and measuring the social accountability of medical schools. World Health Organization, 1995; <http://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/59441>.

37. Boelen C, Pearson D, Kaufman A, Rourke J, Woollard R, Marsh DC, Gibbs T. Producing a socially accountable medical school: AMEE Guide No. 109. *Med Teach*. 2016; 38(11):1078-1091, doi: 10.1080/0142159X.2016.1219029. Epub 2016 Sep 9. PMID: 27608933.

38. Wilkerson L, Doyle L. Developing teachers and developing learners, Chapter 19. In: Dornan TMK, Scherpbier A, Spencer J, editors. *Medical Education: Theory and Practice*. Edinburgh: Churchill-Livingstone; 2011.

39. Frenk J, Chen L, Bhutta ZA, *et al.*. Health professionals for a new century: transforming education to strengthen health systems in an interdependent world. *Lancet* 2010; 376(9756):1923–58, doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(10)61854-5. Epub 2010 Nov 26.

40. Fakoyejo, O. Brain drain in Nigeria will boost remittances, foreign investments, says IMF. *Business*, The Cable, October 14, 2023: <https://www.thecable.ng/brain-drain-in-nigeria-will-boost-remittances-foreign-investments-says-imf/amp/>.